

A Web Version of KomaMRI. Sequence Editor and Remote Execution

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: KomaMRI.jl [1] is a magnetic resonance simulator which is intended to be fast, easy-to-use, extensible, open-source and cross-platform [2]. This tool, developed in the Julia programming language, allows the simulation of any general MRI scenario. To carry out the simulation, it needs two main input arguments: the MRI sequence and the anatomical model --known as phantom-- on which the simulation is applied. This work presents two new functionalities added to the simulator. The first one consists of a graphical sequence editor, which allows the creation of any sequence by means of draggable blocks. These blocks define the basic elements of a sequence, such as RF pulses, gradients, delays or acquisition periods. The second feature is a web version of the simulator. Thanks to it, it is possible to use the tool from a browser, thus enabling the use of the simulator on a remote simulation server with practitioners receiving online courses as prospective users and avoiding the need to install software locally.

METHODS: As for the technologies, Qt has been chosen for developing the graphical sequence editor. Specifically, we chose Qt Quick, a module for interface development based on the QML language. The main advantage of this module, apart from its ease of understanding, is that it is oriented to cross-platform application development. This is due, in part, to the fact that Qt allows compilation to WebAssembly, a low-level code that can be executed in browsers.

In terms of creating the web server and communicating with it, Oxygen.jl has been used. With this new Julia package, it has been possible to develop a REST-based server which receives the input parameters from the client, calls the simulator and returns the result back. Figure 1 shows the application diagram, in which KomaMRI and the sequence editor interfaces are included.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION: The implementation of these two new functionalities has meant a reasonable improvement in the simulator's usability. More specifically, the contributions of this work allow editing sequences comfortably and running the simulator remotely in a crowdsourced way. In addition, powerful computers are no longer needed on the client, since all the computational load is now assumed by the server. All this will be tested in real educational experiences thanks to collaborations with San Carlos Clinical Hospital (Madrid) and the Mar Parc Salut Consortium of Barcelona.

Finally, as future lines of work, improved phantoms are being studied and developed for the simulator, including anatomical and diffusion movements, as well as flow dynamics. Finally, a system for creating and reading this type of data structures is also being developed.

Figure 1: Operation diagram of the application. Client and server elements are shown, as well as the interactions between them.

References

- [1] Castillo-Passi, C, Coronado, R, Varela-Mattatall, G, Alberola-López, C, Botnar, R, Irrazaval, P. KomaMRI.jl: An open-source framework for general MRI simulations with GPU acceleration. *Magn Reson Med.* 2023; 90: 329- 342.
- [2] Villacorta-Aylagas, P, Fernández-Arias, I, Castillo-Passi, C, Irrazaval, P, Simmross-Wattenberg, F, Rodríguez-Cayetano, M, Alberola-López, C: A Cross-Platform Editor and Simulator of Magnetic Resonance Imaging Sequences: Design and Implementation. *CASEIB.* 2022.

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